

ISic0115

I.Sicily inscription 0115

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Dis · Manibus · sac(rum)
2. Callistio · tiraeci · Treb(oni) ·
3. fecit · Spec[i] · eques
4. cons(ervo) · bene merenti
5. v(ixit) · XX

Apparatus

Text based on ILTermini

Gualtherus: CALLISIO·IRAECI

Translation (en)

Sacred to the Shades of the Underworld; to Callistus, a thraex (of Trebonius?).

Spec(i?)es, an eques, made (this) to his well-deserving fellow-slave, who lived 20 years (?).

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285321

EDR 110917

EDCS 22100065

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